

DIDACTIC POSSIBILITIES OF DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL PLATFORMS AND INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Annotation. The present article provides a discussion of the didactic potential of modern digital educational platforms and the use of interactive approaches to teaching foreign languages. The research is aimed at examining the influence of digital technologies on the effectiveness of the educational process, motivation of students, and their ability to communicate. Special attention is paid to multimedia, individualized training, and interactive approaches to teaching.

Keywords: digital education, educational platforms, interactive methods, teaching foreign languages, didactics, technology, communication skills.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada chet tillarini o'qitishda raqamli ta'lim platformalari va interaktiv metodlarning didaktik imkoniyatlari ko'rib chiqiladi. Tadqiqotda raqamli texnologiyalarning ta'lim jarayoni samaradorligini oshirish, talabalarning motivatsiyasini kuchaytirish hamda kommunikativ kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishdagi o'rni tahlil qilinadi. Multimedia resurslaridan foydalanish, ta'limni individuallashtirish va interaktiv o'qitish metodlarini qo'llash masalalariga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan. Shuningdek, zamonaviy chet tillarini o'qitish tizimida raqamli texnologiyalarni joriy etishning afzalliklari va mumkin bo'lgan muammolari ham yoritilgan.

Аннотация. В данной работе будут рассмотрены дидактические возможности цифровых образовательных платформ и интерактивных методов при изучении иностранных языков. Будет проведен анализ применения цифровых технологий для повышения эффективности образовательного процесса, развития мотивации обучения и формирования коммуникативной компетенции учащихся. Особое внимание будет уделено применению мультимедийных источников, индивидуализации учебного процесса.

Fast advancement of information technologies has brought about considerable changes in the process of education and emergence of new opportunities for learning foreign languages. Digital learning resources and interactive ways of teaching have become decisive elements of successful language studies. Digital educational platforms and interactive teaching methods have become key factors in increasing the efficiency of studying foreign languages. They ensure access to educational resources, increase student activity, and help develop communicative skills. The current article explores the didactic capabilities of digital educational platforms and the importance of interactive methods in the teaching of foreign languages. The influence of these factors on the motivation and performance of learners is also considered.

The implementation of digital technologies in the process of studying has become one of the essential elements of modern pedagogic activity. Traditionally used methods of foreign language teaching are now actively supplemented with various innovations and technologies.

The increased usage of online educational resources has led to significant changes in the educational process and interaction between students and their teachers and peers.

Foreign languages imply the necessity of active communication, frequent practice, and acquaintance with the authentic literature. Online educational platforms offer a range of features which help to fulfill these criteria and create an effective learning environment. Thus, the analysis of didactic opportunities of such platforms is quite topical for today.

Digital educational platforms for teaching foreign languages: Digital educational platforms are online systems aimed at simplifying the process of studying via using technology. They offer the possibility to access educational material, assignments, communication options, and assessment system.

Main didactic opportunities of digital educational platforms include: Availability and flexibility: access to the learning resources anytime and anywhere. Flexibility allows the students to learn at their own speed. Individualized learning approach: adaptive learning programs in the educational system enable teachers to adjust the curriculum depending on the students' level of education and preferences. The individualized learning will improve the academic success of students.

Multimedia: text, audio, video, images, and interactive assignments are all included in the online platform. Multimedia learning will improve understanding of the topic for students. Immediate feedback: feedback is provided instantly by means of quizzes and other types of automated testing. Instantaneous feedback allows students to identify mistakes and improve their academic results. Development of self-study skills: technologies enable greater autonomy on the part of the learner, thus fostering independent study, self-evaluation, and critical thinking.

Learning management systems, Internet communication tools, and language learning software can serve as good examples of digital educational platforms currently used in language teaching. Interactive techniques in teaching foreign languages: interactive techniques imply an active involvement of students in the process of learning and their collaboration. They emphasize communication and practical application of knowledge rather than passive memorization.

In foreign language teaching, various interactive techniques are used.: Group discussions: discussion stimulates students to express their opinion, to develop their oral speech and critical thinking. Role-playing games: these games are used to simulate real-life situations in order to train language skills. Project-based learning: students participate in individual or collective projects including research and presentation of results. Gamification: use of educational games and competitions motivates students to study and makes the process more interesting. Co-education: students work together in completing tasks, exchanging ideas and helping each other throughout the process. Interactive approaches provide such an atmosphere when students start to be active participants in the process of knowledge creation.

Combination of digital platforms and interactive methods. Using digital education platforms in combination with interactive methods of teaching contributes to the formation of an efficient educational environment. The teacher may organize discussions, group work, quizzes, and other collaborative learning activities using technology. Thus, students will be able to attend video conferences, complete online assignments, and interact with each other or native speakers. In addition, interacting with technological devices while learning contributes to the development not only of linguistic but also digital literacy skills of the learners. Problems with the implementation. In spite of the many benefits, there are still some problems that can arise during the implementation of digital educational technologies. They

are: limited availability of technological means. Insufficient level of digital competence of both teachers and students. Technical problems and Internet connection. Need for teachers' additional training. It is necessary for educational institutions to solve these problems to increase the efficiency of the digital learning environment.

In conclusion, use of digital educational platforms and interactive teaching methods has greatly enlarged opportunities for learning a foreign language. Introduction of these technologies raises the motivation of students, contributes to individualization of learning process and improvement of communicative skills. Use of digital tools together with interactive learning creates efficient learning environment.

References:

1. Richards, J. C., & Rodgers, T. S. Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching. Cambridge University Press, 2014.
2. Harmer, J. The Practice of English Language Teaching. Pearson Education, 2015.
3. Warschauer, M. Technology and Language Learning. Cambridge University Press, 2011.
4. Hubbard, P. Computer Assisted Language Learning: Critical Concepts in Linguistics. Routledge, 2009.
5. UNESCO. Technology in Education: A Tool on Whose Terms? Paris, 2023.